

ANALYSIS OF PROJECT DRIVERS: RESPONSIBLE MANAGEMENT, INNOVATION, AND CORPORATE REPUTATION ON PROJECT SUCCESS WITH TEAM COLLABORATION AS MODERATOR

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Abstract

Background: Achieving project success is critical for organizational growth and competitiveness. Previous research has identified responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation as important drivers of project outcomes. However, limited studies have explored how these factors interact within project teams and the moderating role of team collaboration in enhancing project performance. Understanding these dynamics is essential for managers to implement strategies that optimize project success.

Objective: The study aims to examine the influence of responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation on project success, while investigating the moderating role of team collaboration in strengthening these relationships.

Methodology: A quantitative, cross-sectional research design was adopted. Data were collected from 272 employees involved in project management across various organizations in Islamabad, Pakistan, using a structured self-administered questionnaire. Constructs measured included responsible management, innovation, corporate reputation, team collaboration, and project success. Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale. Data were analyzed using SPSS 28 for descriptive statistics and SmartPLS for structural equation modeling (SEM) to assess direct and moderating effects. Reliability and validity of constructs were evaluated through Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted.

Results: The demographic analysis showed that respondents were predominantly male (67.65%) and aged 18–30 years (54.04%), with most holding bachelor's degrees (36.77%). All constructs demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = 0.818$ – 0.850) and convergent validity ($AVE > 0.60$). Direct effect analysis revealed that innovation ($B = 0.816$, $p < 0.001$) had the strongest positive impact on project success, followed by team collaboration ($B = 0.226$, $p = 0.001$), corporate reputation ($B = 0.138$, $p = 0.038$), and responsible management ($B = 0.077$, $p = 0.023$). Moderation analysis indicated that team collaboration significantly

strengthened the effects of innovation ($B = 0.125$, $p < 0.001$) and responsible management ($B = 0.063$, $p = 0.039$) on project success, whereas its moderating role with corporate reputation was not significant.

Conclusion: Responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation significantly predict project success, with innovation being the most influential factor. Team collaboration plays a critical moderating role, enhancing the positive effects of responsible management and innovation. These findings emphasize that integrating ethical practices, fostering innovation, maintaining a strong corporate reputation, and promoting collaborative teamwork are essential for achieving sustainable project success.

INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic business environment, achieving project success is crucial for organizational growth and competitiveness. This study examines how responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation influence project success, considering team collaboration as a moderating factor. Responsible management refers to ethical, sustainable, and stakeholder-oriented decision-making, which strengthens trust and supports long-term organizational performance (Tinoco, Sato, & Hasan, 2016). Innovation involves the introduction of creative solutions, processes, or technologies to improve efficiency and organizational adaptability (Garrido-Moreno, Martin-Rojas, & García-Morales, 2024). Corporate reputation reflects how stakeholders perceive the organization and influences the attraction of partners, investors, and skilled employees, thereby impacting project outcomes (Taghian, D'Souza, & Polonsky, 2015). Team collaboration enhances communication, coordination, creativity, and problem-solving, providing a supportive context in which these factors can more effectively contribute to project success (Pineda & Lerner, 2006).

Project success is defined as the achievement of project objectives, value delivered to stakeholders, and adherence to timelines, budgets, and quality standards (Bannerman, 2008). While responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation are individually recognized as key drivers of project performance, there is limited research examining their combined influence on project outcomes. Moreover, the role of team collaboration in moderating these relationships

remains underexplored, creating a critical gap in understanding how project teams can leverage these factors to improve performance. Addressing this gap is important because understanding the interplay between management practices, innovative efforts, organizational reputation, and teamwork can guide managers in implementing strategies that enhance project efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction.

The theoretical foundations of this study draw upon the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Social Exchange Theory (SET). RBV posits that organizations gain a competitive edge through unique, valuable, and inimitable resources (Pereira (Pereira, Novaski, Santos, & Mota, 2022) & Bamel, 2021). Within this framework, responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation constitute strategic resources that can drive project success, while team collaboration functions as a dynamic capability facilitating the effective utilization of these resources. SET conceptualizes social interactions as exchanges in which individuals seek to maximize benefits and minimize costs; positive social interactions within project teams, influenced by responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation, enhance project outcomes, with team collaboration strengthening these exchanges by promoting trust, coordination, and knowledge-sharing (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Additional theoretical perspectives support a deeper understanding of project success. Systems Theory highlights the interdependencies between project factors; Diffusion of Innovation Theory explains the adoption and dissemination of new

practices within project teams; Social Identity Theory emphasizes how group identification shapes collaboration; Contingency Theory of Leadership illustrates that leadership effectiveness depends on context; Transaction Cost Economics evaluates the cost-benefit trade-offs in organizing project activities; Organizational Learning Theory focuses on knowledge acquisition and sharing for performance improvement; and Social Capital Theory underscores the value derived from networks and relationships, which is enhanced by team collaboration.

Empirical research has increasingly shown that responsible management positively affects project outcomes through ethical leadership and stakeholder engagement (Alvarez Tinoco, (Tinoco, Sato, & Hasan, 2016). Innovation plays a crucial role in project success by introducing novel solutions and increasing organisational resilience (Garrido-Moreno, Martín-Rojas, & García-Morales, 2024). Corporate reputation influences project outcomes by attracting resources, partnerships, and stakeholder confidence, while strong project performance further reinforces organizational reputation (Neville, Bell, & Mengüç, 2005). Team collaboration contributes by facilitating communication, knowledge-sharing, creativity, and collective problem-solving, which all strengthen the impact of responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation on project success.

This study is guided by the hypothesis that responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation each have a positive impact on project success. Additionally, team collaboration is expected to moderate these relationships, enhancing the effectiveness of responsible management, improving the implementation of innovative solutions, and amplifying how corporate reputation translates into tangible project outcomes. By investigating these interactions, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that drive project success and offer practical insights for managers and policymakers seeking to improve project performance, ethical standards, and stakeholder trust.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative research design to examine the effects of responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation on project success, with team collaboration as a moderating variable. A cross-sectional survey method was employed to collect data from employees in the business industry of Islamabad, Pakistan. All procedures adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation. The target population comprised employees actively involved in project management and execution within their organizations. The inclusion criteria required participants to be adults aged 20–55 years, currently employed in a project-related role, and willing to provide informed consent. A demographic sheet was used to collect detailed participant information, including age, gender, education level, socioeconomic status, living environment (urban/rural), height, weight, and any relevant medical or occupational complications.

A sample of 300 participants was determined using online calculator with a 5% margin of error, representing the target population adequately. A structured self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data. The survey included validated scales for responsible management (5 items) (Voegtlin, 2011), innovation (5 items) (Fischer, Reuter, & Riedl, 2021), corporate reputation (8 items) (Pratoom, 2010), team collaboration (4 items) (Orchard, King, Khalili, & Bezzina, 2012), and project success (12 items) (Mahaney & Lederer, 2006)).

Data collection involved distributing the questionnaires to participants. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages, were computed to summarize participant characteristics and study variables. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with path analysis and bootstrapping was conducted to test the hypothesized relationships among responsible management, innovation, corporate reputation, team collaboration, and project success. Moderator effects of team collaboration were also evaluated through interaction terms within the SEM framework.

RESULTS

Table-1:
Demographic Profile of Respondents (N=300)

Variable	Category	F(%)
Gender	Male	184 (67.65)
	Female	88 (32.35)
Age	18-30	147 (54.04)
	31-43	67 (24.63)
	44-55	38 (13.97)
	55 and above	20 (7.36)
Qualification	Matriculation	31 (11.40)
	Intermediate	43 (15.81)
	Bachelor	100 (36.77)
	Master	74 (27.20)
	MPhil	24 (8.82)
Marital Status	Married	133 (48.90)
	Single	139 (51.10)
Work Experience	1-10 Years	98 (36.02)
	11-20 Years	51 (18.76)
	21-30 Years	41 (15.07)
	31-40 Years	69 (25.37)
	41-50 Years	13 (4.78)

Table-1 results show that the demographic profile of the respondents was predominantly male (67.65%) compared to female (32.35%). Most participants were in the age group of 18-30 years (54.04%), followed by 31-43 years (24.63%), 44-55 years (13.97%), and 56 years and above (7.36%). Regarding educational qualifications, most respondents held a bachelor's degree (36.77%), followed by a master's degree (27.20%), intermediate education (15.81%),

matriculation (11.40%), and MPhil (8.82%). The marital status distribution was almost even, with 51.10% single and 48.90% married participants. Work experience varied, with the largest proportion having 1-10 years of experience (36.02%), followed by 31-40 years (25.37%), 11-20 years (18.76%), 21-30 years (15.07%), and 41-50 years (4.78%).

Table-2:
Constructs' Reliability and Validity

Constructs	Items	Λ	A	(rho_a)	(rho_c)	AVE
Corporate Reputation (CR)	8	0.741-0.851	0.834	0.866	0.886	0.660
Innovation (INO)	6	0.848-0.899	0.844	0.845	0.906	0.762
Project Success (PS)	12	0.755-0.875	0.850	0.859	0.899	0.690
Responsible Management (RM)	5	0.733-0.831	0.836	0.857	0.833	0.602
Team Collaboration (TC)	12	0.747-0.836	0.818	0.852	0.876	0.639

Composite Reliability (ρ), Factor Loadings (λ)
 Table-2 results show that all constructs exhibited high reliability and validity. Factor loadings (λ) ranged from 0.733 to 0.899 across items, indicating strong individual item contributions to their respective constructs. Cronbach's alpha (α) values ranged from 0.818 to 0.850, confirming internal consistency. Composite reliability

(ρ_c) and ρ_a values were also satisfactory, ranging from 0.833 to 0.906, demonstrating that the constructs reliably measured the intended latent variables. The average variance extracted (AVE) ranged from 0.602 to 0.762, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.50, which confirms convergent validity.

Table -3:
Indirect Relationships (Moderating Effects)

Relationships	B	SE	T	p	Result
TC × CR → PS	0.046	0.028	1.66	0.098	Rejected
TC × INO → PS	0.125	0.028	4.53	<0.001	Accepted
TC × RM → PS	0.063	0.030	2.07	0.039	Accepted

Table-3 results show that the moderating effects of team collaboration on the relationships between corporate reputation, innovation, and responsible management with project success were partially supported. Specifically, the interaction effect of TC × CR → PS was not statistically significant (B = 0.046, t = 1.66, p = 0.098), indicating that team collaboration did not moderate the impact of

project success. In contrast, the interaction effect of TC × INO → PS was highly significant (B = 0.125, t = 4.53, p < 0.001), demonstrating that team collaboration strengthened the positive effect of innovation on project success. Similarly, TC × RM → PS was significant (B = 0.063, t = 2.07, p = 0.039), indicating that collaboration among team members enhanced the impact of responsible management on project outcomes.

Table -4
Direct Effects (RQ1-RQ3)

Relationships	B	SE	t	P	Result
CR → PS	0.138	0.066	2.08	0.038	Accepted
INO → PS	0.816	0.036	22.79	<0.001	Accepted
RM → PS	0.077	0.034	2.28	0.023	Accepted
TC → PS	0.226	0.070	3.22	0.001	Accepted

Table-4 results show that all direct paths from responsible management, innovation, corporate reputation, and team collaboration to project success were statistically significant. Innovation had the strongest direct effect on project success (B = 0.816, t = 22.79, p < 0.001), indicating that projects are most sensitive to innovative practices. Team collaboration also had a notable direct effect (B = 0.226, t = 3.22, p = 0.001), emphasizing its importance in facilitating

successful project outcomes. Responsible management positively influenced project success (B = 0.077, t = 2.28, p = 0.023), showing that ethical decision-making and principled leadership contribute to achieving project objectives. Corporate reputation had a moderate yet significant impact on project success (B = 0.138, t = 2.08, p = 0.038), suggesting that organizations with a strong reputation are better positioned to achieve successful project outcomes.

Table-5
Moderating Effects (RQ4)

Relationships	B	SE	t	p	Result
TC × CR → PS	0.046	0.028	1.66	0.098	Rejected
TC × INO → PS	0.125	0.028	4.53	<0.001	Accepted
TC × RM → PS	0.063	0.030	2.07	0.039	Accepted

Table-5 results show that team collaboration significantly moderated the relationships of innovation and responsible management with project success, but not corporate reputation. The interaction of TC × INO → PS was highly significant (B = 0.125, t = 4.53, p < 0.001), indicating that the presence of strong collaboration amplifies the positive effect of innovation on project performance. Similarly, TC × RM → PS was significant (B = 0.063, t = 2.07, p = 0.039), suggesting that ethical and responsible management practices are more effective when supported by collaborative team environments. In contrast, TC × CR → PS was not significant (B = 0.046, t = 1.66, p = 0.098), indicating that team collaboration does not substantially change the effect of corporate reputation on project outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation on project success, with a particular focus on the moderating role of team collaboration. By investigating these relationships, the study sought to provide theoretical and practical insights into factors that enhance project performance in organizational contexts, particularly within the business industry of Islamabad, Pakistan. The demographic profile of respondents indicated a diverse participant pool, predominantly male (67.65%) and largely aged 18–30 years (54.04%), with a majority holding a bachelor's degree (36.77%) and varying levels of work experience. This diversity enhances the generalizability of the findings within the local context.

The reliability and validity of constructs were evaluated through Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted, with all constructs demonstrating strong internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.818\text{--}0.850$; $\rho_c = 0.833\text{--}0.906$) and adequate convergent validity (AVE > 0.60). Factor loadings ($\lambda = 0.733\text{--}0.899$) indicated that items reliably represented their intended constructs, supporting the robustness of the measurement model and aligning with the recommendations of Attakora et al. (2016), who emphasized the importance of valid and reliable constructs in structural equation modeling for project management research (Attakora-Amaniampong, 2016).

Analysis of the direct effects revealed that all independent variables significantly influenced project success. Innovation had the strongest direct effect (B = 0.816, t = 22.79, p < 0.001), followed by team collaboration (B = 0.226, t = 3.22, p = 0.001), corporate reputation (B = 0.138, t = 2.08, p = 0.038), and responsible management (B = 0.077, t = 2.28, p = 0.023). This consistent with Alvarez Tinoco (2023) positive effect of responsible management highlights the importance of ethical leadership, stakeholder engagement, and principled decision-making in achieving successful project outcomes (Tinoco, Sato, & Hasan, 2016). This is supported by previous findings by Garrido et al., (2024), suggested that the pronounced impact of innovation confirms its central role in enhancing organizational adaptability and project performance, supporting findings by Garrido (Garrido-Moreno, Martín-Rojas, & García-Morales, 2024). The significant relationship between corporate reputation and project success suggests that a strong organizational image facilitates stakeholder trust, resource acquisition,

and collaborative engagement, aligning with the work of Yan et al. (2022), pointed out that corporate reputation and project success facilitate stakeholder trust (Yan, Espinosa-Cristia, Kumari, & Cioca, 2022). The direct effect of team collaboration underscores the critical role of teamwork, coordination, and effective communication in improving project outcomes, consistent with Abejide, et al. (2023), indicates that clear and effective communication patterns (Abejide, 2024). These results collectively support the Resource-Based View and Social Exchange Theory, emphasizing that organizational resources, combined with collaborative team practices, drive competitive advantage and project success.

Team collaboration was examined as a moderator between the independent variables and project success. The results revealed a significant moderating effect for innovation ($B = 0.125$, $t = 4.53$, $p < 0.001$) and responsible management ($B = 0.063$, $t = 2.07$, $p = 0.039$), while the moderation for corporate reputation was not significant ($B = 0.046$, $t = 1.66$, $p = 0.098$). This indicates that collaborative practices enhance the positive effects of responsible management and innovation on project outcomes. Specifically, ethical leadership and principled decision-making are more effective when implemented in a collaborative project environment, enabling shared responsibility, open communication, and joint problem-solving, which is consistent with Muhammad et al. (2024) found that CSFs in supplier partnerships provide valuable insights for construction practitioners, helping them prevent disputes, improve partnership efficiency, and eliminate adversarial interactions (Mahmud & Bakar, 2024). Similarly, collaboration amplified the impact of innovation, showing that innovative solutions are more effectively implemented when team members engage in knowledge sharing and collective problem-solving, corroborating research on organizational learning and innovation (Liu, Liu, Lai, & Li, 2021). The non-significant moderation effect on corporate reputation suggests that while reputation directly influences project outcomes, its effect is relatively independent of collaborative practices, consistent with prior studies

emphasizing the strategic value of reputation in project performance (Olawale, Oyedele, Owolabi, Gbadamosi, & Kusimo, 2022).

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that responsible management, innovation, and corporate reputation are significant predictors of project success, with team collaboration playing a crucial moderating role for responsible management and innovation. Among the examined variables, innovation exerted the strongest influence on project outcomes, highlighting its central role in fostering creativity, adaptability, and efficiency in project execution. Responsible management and corporate reputation also contributed positively, emphasizing the importance of ethical leadership, stakeholder trust, and a strong organizational image. Team collaboration not only directly enhanced project success but also amplified the effects of responsible management and innovation, demonstrating the value of coordinated, communicative, and cooperative project teams. These findings collectively suggest that a combination of ethical practices, innovative approaches, strong reputation, and collaborative teamwork forms the foundation for achieving sustainable project success in organizational contexts.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

From a practical standpoint, organizations should integrate responsible management practices into their project frameworks by promoting ethical decision-making, accountability, and stakeholder engagement. Encouraging innovation through structured methodologies such as Agile, Lean, Design Thinking, and Stage-Gate models can maximize project effectiveness and efficiency. Building and maintaining a strong corporate reputation remains essential for attracting resources, clients, and skilled personnel, thereby facilitating smoother project execution. Furthermore, organizations should foster a culture of team collaboration through open communication, cross-functional teams, and collaborative problem-solving mechanisms, which not only enhance project outcomes directly but

also strengthen the impact of responsible management and innovative practices. Training programs, workshops, and leadership initiatives that reinforce collaborative behavior can further improve project team performance.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study has several limitations. The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference and limits the understanding of how these relationships evolve over time. The sample was confined to employees in the business industry of Islamabad, Pakistan, which may reduce generalizability to other sectors, regions, or cultural contexts. Additionally, reliance on self-reported survey data may introduce bias, including social desirability or response biases. Certain factors influencing project success, such as organizational culture, leadership style, technological readiness, and external environmental factors, were not incorporated, leaving potential unexplored moderating or mediating effects.

Based on these findings, several recommendations can be proposed. Future research should employ longitudinal or experimental designs to establish causal relationships and examine changes over time. Expanding the study to diverse industries and cross-cultural contexts can enhance generalizability and provide broader insights into project management practices. Organizations should implement structured programs to foster responsible management, innovation, and collaboration, such as leadership training, collaborative project planning, and innovation incubation initiatives. Finally, examining additional variables, including technological adoption, organizational culture, or employee motivation, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of factors influencing project success, enabling managers to adopt evidence-based strategies to optimize outcomes and achieve sustainable organizational growth.

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